

ANALYSIS OF CONVENIENT METHODS OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotation: *In today's education system, distance learning is becoming a convenient form of education. Distance education is a form of education in which, in addition to full-time and part-time education, the preferred traditional and innovative methods, tools and forms of education based on computer and telecommunication technologies are widely used in the information process. The educational process is organized in a place that is convenient for the student, based on an individual schedule, with the help of special facilities, telephone, electronic communication and other educational tools.*

Keywords: *Distance learning, development, media, email, process, learning, knowledge, freedom, efficiency, audio-video, animation, graphics, results.*

One of the most important issues in the organization of distance learning is the selection of professors and teachers. In order to implement this type of education, teachers must be selected from the most experienced and organized professors. Because distance learning is different from other types of education, its effectiveness depends in many ways on the knowledge, organizational and managerial characteristics of the teacher. The structure should be responsible for the organization of distance learning in the field. In the next stages, distance learning centers can be established in several higher education institutions specializing in one or different areas.

During the training, the student receives the study materials and assignments on his computer, sends the completed tests and tests to the teacher via the Internet or e-mail. In addition, the listener can ask questions to his teacher and methodologist and get timely answers.

Great attention is paid to the development of distance education in our country. Many people think that distance learning is just a new form of distance learning known to us. To some extent, this is true: a person can actually read without leaving home. But there is one condition: it must be a modern computer with a standard program. The essence of this program is distance education and the inseparability of modern techniques and technologies. Today, a student can study in almost any Western university program without leaving their home

country. Education is becoming more global and universal, ahead of the process of political and economic integration.

Distance learning differs from traditional forms of teaching by the following characteristics.

Flexibility. Opportunity to practice whenever, wherever and at any time. There is no limit to the time allotted for the study of science.

Modularity. Formulation of curricula that meet the needs of individual or group of independent disciplines - modules.

Parallelism. Education in parallel with professional activity or study in other educational institutions.

Social equality. Equality of access to education, regardless of the student's place of residence, state of health, and financial means.

The quality of distance learning as a full-time form of education does not depend on the involvement of prominent teaching staff and the use of the best teaching methods and control tests in the learning process. They include a set of all pedagogical acts in the relationship between teacher and student. Distance learning is based on the latest achievements in the field of educational technology, based on innovative computer technology and telecommunications, along with traditional teaching aids. Most of the educational and scientific materials form a virtual-information-educational environment due to the remoteness of the audience.

Electronic publications for the educational process have all the features of paper publications, but also have many advantages and disadvantages. In particular, it has a compact storage in computer memory or disk, hypertext capabilities, duplication, the ability to quickly make changes and additions, the ability to send information by e-mail, an automated learning system. Includes didactic, methodological and informational materials and software for the curriculum and allows them to be used comprehensively in independent learning and control.

Distance learning has the following advantages:

a) creative learning environment. Based on the many methods available, the teacher provides knowledge, and the student reads only the given material. Based on the distance learning offered, students will be able to search for the information they need from a computer-based database and, of course, share their experiences with others through electronic networks. This ensures that students communicate well with others and, in turn, encourages such hard learning.

b) The possibility of independent study. Distance learning includes primary, secondary, university, part-time and evening courses. Inspectors with varying levels of training can work on their own individual lesson schedules and interact with students at their level.

d) Significant changes in the workplace. Distance learning provides millions of people, especially those who are part-time. Teaching based on this method plays a very important role in the training of personnel, that is, it is possible to acquire knowledge in the workplace without geographical and financial difficulties.

e) A new and effective means of teaching and learning. Statistics show that distance learning is just as effective as distance learning. In addition, distance learning goes beyond the limits set by the university. The advantage of students studying on this basis is that they are provided with the best, quality materials and teachers.

Another advantage of distance learning is that the student can study at a time convenient to him, and even without leaving work. It is because of these advantages that this style is becoming more and more popular in the world. Many large companies use this method to improve or retrain their skills, saving millions of dollars a year. begins reading, masters the materials under the supervision of a teacher. It is determined by the performance of mastering tasks, tests. The faster the listeners and students master the task, the faster they will complete the course and study and get a certificate. If he is unable to master the program, he will be able to work independently and continue his studies. Distance learning also has organizational and economic advantages. Audiences and dormitories are not required for distance learning.

REFERENCES:

1. ХАЙТБАЙЕВНА НОСИРОВА, М. (2021). ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL (TIPOLOGICAL) CLASSIFICATION OF LANGUAGES *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 7, 155-157. Retrieved from <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/106>

2. Saidova, Makhsudakhon Abbasovna WAYS TO EVALUATE THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS AND ITS FORMATION // ORIENSS. 2021. №Special Issue 2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-evaluate-the-professional-competence-of-teachers-and-its-formation> (дата обращения: 24.03.2022).

3. Абдуллаева Марҳабо Раҳмонкуловна, (2020). 'ИНСОНИЯТНИНГ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТИДАГИ МИЛЛИЙ КОЛОРИТНИ ИФОДАЛОВЧИ ФЕЪЛЛИ ФРАЗЕМАЛАР (Агата кристи асарлари талкинида)' "МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИЯ ВА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ: АНЪАНАЛАР ВА ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ИЛМИЙ МАКТАБЛАРИ" республика илмий-амалий конференцияси илмий тўплами, 153-158.
4. Javliyeva Dilafruz Rustam qizi. (2021). THE COMMUNICATIVE NATURE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK KINSHIP TERMINOLOGY. *Archive of Conferences*, 14(1), 3-4. Retrieved from <https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/604>
5. Akramxodjaeva, D., M. Nasretdinova, and M. Abdullayeva. "Translation of national events and concepts in fiction." *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research* 9.2 (2020): 2984-2986.
6. Abduganiyevna, Akramxodjayeva D. "Effective Teaching of a Foreign Language Through a Contextual Approach." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 180-181.
7. Abdujabborova Kamola Husniddin Qizi IMPROVING LITERACY SKILLS THROUGH LEARNING READING // Наука и образование сегодня. 2021. №4 (63). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/improving-literacy-skills-through-learning-reading> (дата обращения: 16.03.2022).